

Design and Evaluation of AGRISHELCHRO-STRHASIS: A Solar-Powered IoT-Based Smart Irrigation and Shading System for Small-Scale Farming

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Abstract

Global environmental challenges, particularly climate change, are significantly impacting agricultural productivity and sustainability, posing risks to food and nutrition security. In response, various technological innovations, such as automated shading, irrigation systems, rainwater harvesting, and solar tracking, have been developed to mitigate these effects and improve resource efficiency.

This study developed an integrated agricultural shelter system, AGRISHELCHRO-STRHASIS, which combines these technologies into a single functional unit. The system is designed to monitor environmental conditions and respond accordingly through automated mechanisms. Specifically, it regulates plant exposure to excessive heat through automated shading, monitors soil moisture to optimize irrigation, utilizes solar tracking to maximize energy efficiency, and incorporates rainwater harvesting to ensure sustainable water use. Results from system testing and user evaluation indicate that the system effectively responds to environmental changes by regulating temperature exposure, maintaining optimal soil moisture levels, conserving energy through solar power utilization, and efficiently collecting and using rainwater. Consequently, the system contributed to maintaining plant growth, yield, and overall health. These findings suggest that AGRISHELCHRO-STRHASIS offers a viable and sustainable solution to address climate-related agricultural challenges through integrated smart technologies.

Keywords: Agricultural Shelter, Automated Shading, Rainwater Harvesting, Smart Irrigation, Solar Tracking

Introduction

Climate change poses a significant global threat to food and nutrition security. As greenhouse gas emissions increase, global temperatures rise due to the greenhouse effect (Malhi et al., 2021). Fu and Walker (2023) demonstrated that under fluctuating light conditions, photosynthesis exhibits a delayed induction response, preventing the immediate attainment of maximum CO₂ assimilation rates. These rapid changes can reduce photosynthetic efficiency and overall crop productivity.

To address these challenges, various technological innovations have been developed and implemented worldwide. In India, automated greenhouse shading systems regulate light exposure to optimize plant growth (Poyen et al., 2017). In China, shading technologies have

been shown to improve plant growth and flower quality, although they produce different physiological responses compared to full sunlight exposure (Huo et al., 2018). In Oklahoma, USA, smart irrigation systems utilize meteorological and soil moisture data to improve water efficiency and minimize waste (Gotcher et al., 2017). Meanwhile, Malaysia has implemented rainwater harvesting systems to address water scarcity and support agricultural applications such as irrigation and vertical farming (Razali et al., 2023). In South England, solar energy is recognized as a sustainable and environmentally friendly source of renewable power (Maka & Alabid, 2022). These advancements demonstrate how innovation and technology are being leveraged to mitigate climate-related challenges in agriculture.

In the Philippines, climate-related risks such as extreme heat and drought have become increasingly severe. On April 7, 2024, the Philippine Atmospheric, Geophysical, and Astronomical Services Administration (PAGASA) reported dangerously high heat index levels in several areas, including Laoag City, Dagupan City, Tuguegarao City, Aparri, Puerto Princesa, Daet, and Cotabato City, with temperatures reaching up to 51°C (Gomez, 2024). These extreme conditions pose serious risks to agricultural productivity and, consequently, to food and nutrition security. At the local level, South Cotabato is experiencing significant agricultural challenges due to prolonged drought and inefficient irrigation systems. Farmers in Polomolok have reported water shortages caused by declining water supply, further exacerbated by climate phenomena such as El Niño. The Office of the Provincial Agriculturist reported that approximately 3,000 farmers across South Cotabato have been affected, resulting in damage to corn crops, irrigation systems, and rice fields (Rebollido, 2024).

In response to these challenges, this study developed and evaluated the effectiveness of AGRISHEL-CRO-STRH-SIS, an integrated agricultural shelter system. The system is designed to harness solar energy, conserve rainwater, regulate plant exposure to excessive heat, and automate irrigation based on real-time environmental data. Using Internet of Things (IoT) technology, microcontrollers, and sensors, the system minimizes human error, enhances climate resilience, and improves plant productivity.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a developmental–descriptive–evaluative research design to develop and assess the integrated agricultural system. The system was deployed across three agricultural sites in Barangay Maligo, Polomolok, South Cotabato (6°19'50" N 125°06'10" E), to evaluate its performance under natural conditions. In addition, the system was evaluated by the farmers in terms of environmental monitoring and response, resource management and efficiency, and system impact on plant growth and health.

The system development followed the V-Model (Verification and Validation Model), which guided the structured process from requirement gathering, system analysis, and design to coding, followed by unit, integration, system, and acceptance testing. The V-Model ensured that each development phase corresponded with a validation phase to verify system functionality and performance.

Figure 1. V-Model of System Development and Testing for AGRISHELCRO-STRHASIS

System performance was assessed using descriptive statistics for temperature regulation, soil moisture, water use, solar energy utilization, and plant growth. In addition, a user-based evaluation was conducted to assess the system’s functionality and usability through structured questionnaires.

Requirement Specification

The system requirements for AGRISHELCRO-STRHASIS were defined to support efficient and sustainable agricultural operations. The system is designed as a solar-powered platform that automates irrigation and shading while monitoring environmental conditions in real time. It utilizes hardware components such as a soil moisture sensor, rainwater sensor, DC motors, Arduino Uno, ESP32, and a solar panel to enable sensing, control, and energy supply. Software components, including the Arduino IDE and Blynk support system, provide programming, monitoring, and control. These components work together to regulate irrigation, manage shading, and optimize resource use, ensuring minimal human intervention and improved plant growth conditions.

System Design

The system architecture of AGRISHELCRO-STRHASIS (See Figure 2) uses an Input-Process-Output (IPO) model. Environmental inputs such as temperature, soil moisture, rainfall, and solar energy are collected through sensors and processed by the system to enable automated control. The system regulates irrigation, shading, and energy utilization, producing outputs such as environmental monitoring, soil moisture assessment, rainfall detection, and real-time data. This setup supports efficient resource use and improved plant growth with minimal human intervention.

Figure 2. System Architecture of AGRISHEL CRO-STRHISIS

Figure 3 illustrates the solar-tracking hardware design for AGRISHEL CRO-STRHISIS, showing the detailed configuration and interactions among the system components. The system uses an LDR array to detect light intensity for solar tracking, while the Arduino Uno serves as the main control unit, processing sensor inputs and controlling the actuators. Servo motors are used to adjust the position of the solar panel for optimal energy capture. Power is supplied by the solar panel and stored in the battery/energy storage unit to ensure continuous operation. The ESP32 module enables wireless communication, allowing data transmission to a mobile device via the Blynk interface for remote monitoring. This configuration demonstrates an integrated hardware system capable of real-time sensing, automated control, and efficient energy utilization to support smart agricultural operations.

Figure 3. Solar Tracking Hardware Design of AGRISHEL CRO-STRHISIS

Figure 4 illustrates the hardware design of the rainwater harvesting subsystem of AgriShelCro-STRHASIS. The system utilizes rainwater sensors to detect rainfall conditions, which serve as input signals to the Arduino Uno for processing. The microcontroller activates the servo motors to regulate the flow of water into the storage system. The collected water is directed into a water container through a controlled piping mechanism, ensuring efficient storage and utilization of rainwater. The system is powered by a power supply unit, while the ESP32 module enables wireless communication, transmitting data to a mobile device for real-time monitoring. This configuration allows automated rainwater collection, minimizes water waste, and enhances resource efficiency, contributing to sustainable agricultural practices.

Figure 4. Rainwater Harvesting Hardware Design of AGRISHELCRO-STRHASIS

Figure 5. Automatic Irrigation Hardware Design of AGRISHELCRO-STRHASIS

Figure 5 shows the hardware design of the automatic irrigation system that highlights the interaction between input, processing, and output components. Soil moisture sensors serve as the input devices, collecting real-time data on soil conditions from multiple points

to ensure accurate monitoring. The Arduino Uno functions as the central controller, processing sensor data and determining whether irrigation is required based on set thresholds. When the soil moisture level is low, it sends a signal to the motor driver, which activates the water pump. The ESP32 module enables wireless communication by transmitting system data to a mobile phone for remote monitoring and control. The water pump draws water from the container and distributes it through PVC pipes to irrigate the soil. The motor driver and power supply ensure proper operation of the pump.

Figure 6. Auto Shading System Hardware Design of AGRISHEL CRO-STRHASIS

Figure 6 shows the auto shading system composed of input, control, and output components. The DHT11 sensor measures temperature and humidity and sends data to the Arduino Uno, which determines when shading is needed. The ESP32 enables communication with a mobile phone for monitoring. The Arduino then signals the motor driver to control two motors: one releases the net, and the other retracts it.

Development and Construction

Figure 6. Functional Diagram of AGRISHEL CRO-STRHASIS

The AGRISHELCRO-STRHASIS was developed through hardware assembly, system integration, and testing. Initially, essential components such as solar panels, sensors, motors, and microcontrollers (Arduino Uno and ESP32) were selected and assembled. These components were then properly connected to form a functional system. Sensors were configured to measure environmental parameters, such as soil moisture and light intensity, and were interfaced with the controllers for data acquisition. Mechanical components, including motors, were installed to automate irrigation and shading processes based on sensor readings. The microcontrollers were programmed to interpret sensor data and execute corresponding actions, enabling automated system responses. Integration of all subsystems was performed to ensure smooth communication between components. The system was tested to verify proper functionality, and necessary adjustments in wiring and code were made to improve performance and ensure reliability.

Unit Testing

The AGRISHELCRO-STRHASIS system underwent unit testing to ensure that each hardware and software component functioned as intended. During this stage, individual sensors, such as soil moisture and rainwater sensors, were evaluated for accuracy and reliability. Additionally, each motor, controller, and power supply unit was tested to verify proper operation, responsiveness, and stability.

Table 1. *Unit Testing of Hardware Components of AGRISHELCRO-STRHASIS*

Module	Functionality	Test ID	Remarks
Soil Moisture Sensor	Detects the moisture levels to automate irrigation	UT-H01	Accurately detected varying moisture levels and responded consistently.
Rainwater Sensor	Detects the presence of rainwater and triggers the opening of the cover for collection.	UT-H02	Successfully detected water and activated the mechanism.
DC Motors	Controls the automated shading mechanism.	UT-H03	Operated smoothly with correct movement.
Water Pump	Pumps water from the container to the irrigation system.	UT-H04	Delivered consistent water flow during operation.
Motor Driver	Regulates and supplies power to motors based on control signals from the Arduino.	UT-H05	Effectively controlled motor speed and direction without overheating.
Arduino Uno	Processes sensor data and control system actions based on inputs.	UT-H06	Accurately executed programmed logic and coordinated all components.
ESP32	Enables wireless communication between system components.	UT-H07	Successfully transmitted data to the mobile device with minimal delay.
Solar Panel	Generates electrical power for the entire system using sunlight.	UT-H08	Provided stable power under adequate sunlight conditions.
Power Supply or Battery	Stores and supplies stable electrical energy to the system.	UT-H09	Maintained consistent voltage and supported continuous operation.

Table 2. *Unit Testing of Software Components of AGRISHELCHRO-STRHASIS*

Module	Functionality	Test ID	Remarks
Arduino IDE	Development environment for writing, compiling, and uploading code to Arduino Uno and ESP32 microcontrollers.	UT-S01	Successfully compiled and uploaded code without errors.
Embedded Firmware	Implements system logic, including sensor data processing and control of actuators.	UT-S02	Accurately executed programmed instructions and responded to sensor inputs.
Blynk Mobile Application	Provides a user interface for real-time monitoring and remote control of the system.	UT-S03	Displayed real-time data and allowed effective remote operation.
Wi-Fi Communication Protocol	Enables data transmission between the ESP32 and the mobile application.	UT-S04	Maintained stable and consistent communication with minimal delay.

Integration Test

After individual component testing, system integration testing was conducted to ensure the smooth operation of the AGRISHELCHRO-STRHASIS. Sensors for temperature, humidity, soil moisture, and rainfall were interfaced with the Arduino Uno, allowing collected data to be processed and transmitted in real time through the ESP32 and IoT platform. The IoT system was further tested to verify its capability to provide real-time data to the user and enable remote control of system functions, including irrigation and automated shading. This feature enhances user awareness and confidence by allowing continuous monitoring of environmental conditions affecting plant growth.

Table 3. *System Integration Test of AGRISHELCHRO-STRHASIS*

Test Name	Modules Involved	Functionality	Test ID	Remarks
Soil Moisture Data Transmission	Soil Moisture Sensor → Arduino Uno	Transmits soil moisture data for irrigation control.	IT-01	Data was accurately received and processed.
Rainwater Detection Integration	Rainwater Sensor → Arduino Uno	Detects rainfall and triggers system response.	IT-02	Successfully triggered appropriate system actions.
Environmental Monitoring Integration	Temperature and Humidity Sensor → Arduino Uno	Provides environmental data or shading decisions.	IT-03	Readings were stable and consistent.
Control Signal Transmission	Arduino Uno → Motor Driver	Sends control signals to actuators.	IT-04	Signals were correctly interpreted by the driver.
Shading Mechanism Control	Motor Driver → DC Motors	Controls the deployment and retraction of the shading system.	IT-05	Motors responded with correct movement and timing.

Continuation

Irrigation System Activation	Motor Driver → Water Pump	Activates the water pump based on soil moisture level.	IT-06	The pump operated efficiently when triggered.
Data Communication Transfer	Arduino Uno → ESP32	Transfers processed data for communication.	IT-07	Data transmission was stable and continuous.
IoT Data Monitoring	ESP32 → Blynk IoT Platform	Sends real-time system data to a mobile application.	IT-08	Data is displayed in real time with minimal delay.
Remote System Control	Blynk → System	Enables the user to control irrigation and shading remotely.	IT-09	Commands were executed correctly by the system.
Power Generation Integration	Solar Panel → Power System	Supplies electrical energy to the system.	IT-10	Provided sufficient and stable power.
Power Distribution Integration	Power Supply → All components	Distributes regulated power across components.	IT-11	Maintained consistent voltage throughout operation.
Full System Operation	All modules	Ensures overall system functionality and coordination.	IT-12	The system operated smoothly and responded accurately.

Acceptance Test

An acceptance test was conducted to verify that the AGRISHEL CRO-STRHASIS system operates effectively in a controlled agricultural environment. Various environmental conditions were simulated to evaluate the performance of the rainwater and soil moisture sensors. The testing focused on key system requirements, including rain detection, accurate soil moisture measurement, automatic irrigation activation, data logging, and user interface usability. The results confirmed that the system met the specified requirements and effectively supported water resource management for crop production.

Table 4. Acceptance Test for AGRISHEL CRO-STRHASIS

Module	Functionality	Test ID	Remarks
Rain Detection and Collection	Detect rain and initiate the water collection process.	AT-01	System successfully detected rain and activated the collection process.
Soil Moisture Measurement	Measure soil moisture accurately.	AT-02	Sensor readings were accurate and consistent across trials.
Automated Irrigation Activation	Activate irrigation when soil moisture is below the threshold.	AT-03	Irrigation system triggered correctly under dry conditions.
Shading System Operation	Automatically control shading mechanisms based on environmental conditions.	AT-04	Shading system deployed and retracted as expected.

Continuation

Data Logging	Record rainwater collection and soil moisture data.	AT-05	Data was logged accurately and stored for monitoring.
IoT Monitoring and Control	Provide real-time monitoring and remote control via a mobile application.	AT-06	Data was displayed in real time, and commands were executed successfully.
Power System Reliability	An operating system using a solar power supply	AT-07	The system functioned continuously under solar power conditions.
User Interface Usability	Ensure the system is user-friendly for farmers.	AT-08	The interface was easy to use and provided clear real-time information.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers followed a systematic process to gather data for the study. The necessary components were then identified and acquired, followed by the development and integration of the AGRISHEL CRO-STRHESIS. After development, the system underwent testing and validation procedures to ensure its functionality and reliability.

For the evaluation phase, a structured evaluation tool written in Bisaya was utilized to assess the system's performance and usability. The instrument was validated by three experts to ensure its reliability and appropriateness. The validated tool was then administered to five farmer-participants selected through purposive sampling. These participants were residents of Barangay Maligo, Polomolok, South Cotabato, specifically from Purok Miranda (6°19'50" N, 125°06'10" E), and possessed prior knowledge relevant to the study. The system was tested across three study sites within the area to ensure consistency of performance under varying conditions. The participants' responses were collected and analyzed to determine the effectiveness of the system.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The data gathered from the evaluation of the AGRISHEL CRO-STRHESIS were analyzed using descriptive statistics, particularly the weighted mean, to determine the level of system performance and usability based on the responses of the participants. The responses obtained from the evaluation tool were quantified using a Likert scale, where each response corresponds to a numerical value. The weighted mean was computed to summarize the overall assessment of each criterion. The results were then analyzed to determine the overall effectiveness, functionality, and usability of the system.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers ensured that all ethical standards were observed throughout the conduct of the study. Before data collection, permission was obtained from the participants, and the purpose of the study was clearly explained to them. Participation was voluntary, and the participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. Informed consent was secured from all participants before the administration of the evaluation tool. The researchers also ensured that the information gathered was treated with confidentiality and used solely for academic purposes.

Results and Discussion

Unit Testing

Each sensor underwent unit testing to verify its functionality and performance. This process ensured that all sensors were operational, reliable, and capable of delivering accurate readings under varying conditions. Unit testing was essential in confirming that each module functioned independently as a single, fully operational unit.

Table 5. *Unit Testing Results of Hardware Components of AGRISHEL CRO-STRHASIS*

Test ID	Module	Expected Output	Actual Results	Remarks
UT-H01	Soil Moisture Sensor	Detect varying soil moisture levels.	The sensor detected moisture accurately and consistently.	Passed
UT-H02	Rainwater Sensor	Detect presence of rainwater and trigger a response.	The sensor detected water and activated the mechanism.	Passed
UT-H03	DC Motors	Control the shading mechanism movement.	Motors operated smoothly with correct movement.	Passed
UT-H04	Water Pump	Pump water to the irrigation system when triggered.	The pump delivered a consistent water flow.	Passed
UT-H05	Motor Driver	Regulate power and control motor operation.	Motor driver controlled speed and direction without overheating.	Passed
UT-H06	Arduino Uno	Process sensor data and execute control actions.	Arduino executed the programmed logic accurately.	Passed
UT-H07	ESP32	Enable wireless communication between components.	Data transmitted successfully with minimal delay.	Passed
UT-H08	Solar Panel	Generate electrical power from sunlight.	Provided stable power under adequate sunlight.	Passed
UT-H09	Power Supply or Battery	Supply stable electrical energy to the system.	Maintained consistent voltage during operation.	Passed

Table 6. *Unit Testing Results of Software Components of AGRISHEL CRO-STRHASIS*

Test ID	Module	Expected Output	Actual Results	Remarks
UT-S01	Arduino IDE	Compile and upload code without errors	Code compiled and uploaded successfully without errors.	Passed
UT-S02	Embedded Firmware	Execute system logic and respond to sensor inputs.	The program executed accurately and responded correctly to inputs.	Passed
UT-S03	Blynk Mobile Application	Display real-time data and enable remote control.	Real-time data is displayed, and remote commands are executed effectively.	Passed
UT-S04	Wi-Fi Communication Protocol	Transmit data between the ESP32 and the mobile application.	Communication remained stable with minimal delay.	Passed

The results of the unit testing for both hardware and software components of the AGRISHELCRO-STRHASIS indicate that all modules functioned according to their intended design. All hardware components, including sensors, actuators, controllers, and power systems, successfully met their expected outputs and demonstrated consistent and reliable performance under testing conditions. The sensors accurately detected environmental parameters, while the actuators responded effectively to control signals. The Arduino Uno and ESP32 ensured proper processing and communication within the system. The software components performed as expected during unit testing. The Arduino IDE successfully compiled and uploaded the system code, while the embedded firmware accurately executed system logic and responded to sensor inputs. The Blynk mobile application provided real-time monitoring and control, and the Wi-Fi communication protocol maintained stable and efficient data transmission.

Integration Testing

After the completion of unit testing, all system modules underwent integration testing to verify their compatibility and ensure seamless interaction among components. These tests were conducted systematically to evaluate the coordinated operation of the system, and the corresponding results are presented in the succeeding table.

Table 7. *System Integration Test Results of AGRISHELCRO-STRHASIS*

Test ID	Test Name	Expected Output	Actual Results	Remarks
IT-01	Soil Moisture Data Transmission	Soil moisture data is transmitted accurately to the controller.	The data was accurately received and processed.	Passed
IT-02	Rainwater Detection Integration	The system detects rainfall and triggers an appropriate response.	The rain detection successfully triggered system actions.	Passed
IT-03	Environmental Monitoring Integration	Environmental data is transmitted accurately for shading decisions.	Readings were stable and consistent.	Passed
IT-04	Control Signal Transmission	Control signals are sent correctly to actuators.	Signals were correctly interpreted by the driver.	Passed
IT-05	Shading Mechanism Control	Motors operate correctly for shading deployment and retraction.	Motors responded with correct movement and timing.	Passed
IT-06	Irrigation System Activation	The water pump is activated based on the soil moisture level.	The pump operated efficiently when triggered.	Passed
IT-07	Data Communication Transfer	Processed data is transmitted reliably to the ESP32.	Data transmission was stable and continuous.	Passed
IT-08	IoT Data Monitoring	Real-time system data is displayed on a mobile application.	Data was displayed in real time with minimal delay.	Passed

Continuation

IT-09	Remote System Control	System responds to remote user commands.	Commands were executed correctly by the system.	Passed
IT-10	Power Generation Integration	Solar panel supplies sufficient electrical energy.	Provided stable and sufficient power.	Passed
IT-11	Power Distribution Integration	Power is distributed consistently across components.	Maintained consistent voltage throughout operation.	Passed
IT-12	Full System Operation	The system operates seamlessly as a complete unit.	The system operated smoothly and responded accurately.	Passed

Table 7 presents the results of the system integration testing of the AGRISHEL CRO-STRHASIS. All test cases yielded a “Passed” result, indicating that the system components operated cohesively and met the expected functional requirements. Data transmission from sensors to the controller was accurate and consistent, while communication between the Arduino, ESP32, and mobile application remained stable with minimal delay. The actuators, including the motors and water pump, responded correctly to control signals, ensuring proper execution of irrigation and shading mechanisms. The power subsystem, composed of the solar panel and power supply, provided stable and sufficient energy for continuous operation.

Acceptance Testing

After the completion of integration testing, acceptance testing was conducted to evaluate the overall performance of the AGRISHEL CRO-STRHASIS in meeting the specified system requirements. This phase focused on validating the system’s functionality, usability, and effectiveness in a real or simulated agricultural environment.

Table 8. *Acceptance Testing Results of AGRISHEL CRO-STRHASIS*

Test ID	Module	Expected Output	Actual Results	Remarks
AT-01	Rain Detection and Collection	Detect rain and initiate the water collection process.	The system detected rain and activated the collection process.	Passed
AT-02	Soil Moisture Measurement	Measure soil moisture accurately.	Sensor readings were accurate and consistent across trials.	Passed
AT-03	Automated Irrigation Activation	Activate irrigation when soil moisture is below the threshold.	Irrigation system triggered correctly under dry conditions.	Passed
AT-04	Shading System Operation	Automatically control the shading mechanism based on environmental conditions.	Shading system deployed and retracted as expected.	Passed
AT-05	Data Logging	Record rainwater collection and soil moisture data.	Data was logged accurately and stored for monitoring.	Passed
AT-06	IoT Monitoring and Control	Provide real-time monitoring and remote control via a mobile application.	Data is displayed in real time, and commands are executed successfully.	Passed

Continuation

AT-07	Power System Reliability	An operating system using a solar power supply.	The system functioned continuously under solar power conditions.	Passed
AT-08	User Interface Usability	Ensure the system is user-friendly for farmers.	The interface was easy to use and provided clear real-time information.	Passed

Table 8 presents the results of the acceptance testing of the AGRISHEL CRO-STRHASIS. All test cases resulted in a “Passed,” indicating that the system successfully met the specified functional and usability requirements. The system effectively detected environmental conditions, such as rainfall and soil moisture, and responded appropriately through automated irrigation and shading mechanisms. The system demonstrated reliable data logging and real-time monitoring capabilities through the IoT platform, while maintaining stable operation using solar power. The user interface was also found to be accessible and easy to use by the participants.

IoT-Based Sensor Data Collected from Three Study Sites of AgriShelCro-STRHASIS

This section presents the IoT-based sensor data collected from the three study sites of the AGRISHEL CRO-STRHASIS. The data were obtained through the system’s integrated sensors, including soil moisture sensors, rainfall sensors, light-dependent resistors (LDR), and the DHT11 temperature and humidity sensor.

Table 9. Soil Moisture Sensor Readings Across Three Sites

Site	Sensor	Sensor Output (ADC Value)	Interpretation
1	SMS 1	465	Damp
	SMS 2	480	Damp
	SMS 3	485	Damp
	SMS 4	476	Damp
	Average	476.50	Damp
2	SMS 1	1003	Dry
	SMS 2	970	Dry
	SMS 3	965	Dry
	SMS 4	980	Dry
	Average	979.50	Dry
3	SMS 1	848	Slightly Dry
	SMS 2	843	Slightly Dry
	SMS 3	836	Slightly Dry
	SMS 3	850	Slightly Dry
	Average	844.25	Slightly Dry

Note: 950 – 1023: Dry, 800 – 949: Slightly Dry, 500 – 799: Moist, and 0 – 499: Damp

Table 9 presents the soil moisture sensor readings across the three study sites of the AGRISHEL CRO-STRHASIS. The results reveal distinct variations in soil moisture conditions. Site 1 recorded the lowest average sensor output (476.50 ADC), indicating damp soil conditions, while Site 2 exhibited the highest average value (979.50 ADC), corresponding to dry soil. Site 3 showed intermediate values (844.25 ADC), interpreted as slightly dry. These variations demonstrate the system’s ability to differentiate soil moisture levels across locations, which is essential for implementing site-specific irrigation strategies.

Table 10. Rainfall Sensor Readings Across Three Sites

Site	Sensor	Sensor Output (ADC Value)	Interpretation
1	RS 1	635	No Rainfall Detected
	RS 2	635	No Rainfall Detected
	RS 3	635	No Rainfall Detected
	RS 4	635	No Rainfall Detected
	Average	635.00	No Rainfall Detected
2	RS 1	430	No Rainfall Detected
	RS 2	430	No Rainfall Detected
	RS 3	430	No Rainfall Detected
	RS 4	430	No Rainfall Detected
	Average	430.00	No Rainfall Detected
3	RS 1	430	No Rainfall Detected
	RS 2	430	No Rainfall Detected
	RS 3	430	No Rainfall Detected
	RS 4	430	No Rainfall Detected
	Average	430.00	No Rainfall Detected

Note: 900 – 1023: Rainfall Detected, 650 – 899: Possible Moisture/Light Rain, 0 – 649: No Rainfall Detected

Table 10 presents the rainfall sensor readings across the three study sites of the AGRISHEL CRO-STRHASIS. The results show that all sensor outputs in Sites 1, 2, and 3 fall within the range of 0–649 ADC values, which corresponds to no rainfall detected. Site 1 recorded a higher average value (635.00 ADC) compared to Sites 2 and 3 (430.00 ADC), indicating that while no rainfall was present, Site 1 may have had slightly higher surface moisture or environmental humidity affecting the sensor readings. The consistency of readings across all sensors within each site suggests stable sensor performance and proper calibration. The uniform interpretation of “no rainfall detected” across all sites confirms that the system accurately identified dry conditions during the testing period.

Table 11. Light Dependent Resistor (LDR) Readings Across Three Sites

Site	Sensor	Sensor Output (ADC Value)	Interpretation
1	LDR 1	790	Low Light Intensity
	LDR 2	780	Low Light Intensity
	LDR 3	800	Low Light Intensity
	LDR 4	805	Low Light Intensity
	Average	793.75	Low Light Intensity
2	LDR 1	1002	High Light Intensity
	LDR 2	1005	High Light Intensity
	LDR 3	1002	High Light Intensity
	LDR 4	1004	High Light Intensity
	Average	1003.25	High Light Intensity
3	LDR 1	1003	High Light Intensity
	LDR 2	1005	High Light Intensity
	LDR 3	1004	High Light Intensity
	LDR 4	1002	High Light Intensity
	Average	1003.50	High Light Intensity

Note: 1000 – 1023: High Light Intensity, 850 – 999: Moderate Light Intensity, 500 – 849: Low Light Intensity, 0 – 499: No Light/Very Low Light

Table 11 presents the light intensity readings obtained from the Light Dependent Resistors (LDR) across the three study sites of the AGRISHEL CRO-STRHASIS. The results

show clear variation in light conditions among the sites. Site 1 recorded lower average values (793.75 ADC), which correspond to low light intensity, while Sites 2 and 3 exhibited significantly higher average readings (1003.25 and 1003.50 ADC, respectively), indicating high light intensity. The consistency of sensor readings within each site suggests stable performance and reliable detection of light conditions. The lower light intensity observed in Site 1 may be attributed to environmental factors such as cloud cover, shading from nearby structures, or vegetation. In contrast, the high light intensity recorded in Sites 2 and 3 indicates strong sunlight exposure, which is essential for plant growth but may also require regulation to prevent excessive heat or light stress. These findings demonstrate that the AGRISHELCRO-STRHASIS effectively detects variations in light intensity across different locations. This capability is important for the system's automated shading mechanism, as it allows the system to respond appropriately to high light conditions by providing shade when necessary.

Table 12. DHT11 Temperature and Humidity Readings Across Three Sites

Site	Sensor	Temperature (°C)	Interpretation	Humidity (%)	Interpretation
1	DHT11	31	Moderate Temperature	40	Moderate Humidity
2	DHT11	37	High Temperature	24	Low Humidity
3	DHT11	34	Moderate Temperature	26	Low Humidity

Note Temperature is classified as Low (20–30°C), Moderate (31–35°C), and High (≥36°C), while humidity is classified as Low (<40%), Moderate (40–60%), and High (>60%).

Table 12 presents the temperature and humidity readings obtained from the DHT11 sensor across the three study sites of the AGRISHELCRO-STRHASIS. The results indicate noticeable variations in environmental conditions among the sites. Site 1 recorded a temperature of 31°C and humidity of 40%, which falls under moderate temperature and moderate humidity conditions. In contrast, Site 2 exhibited the highest temperature at 37°C and the lowest humidity at 24%, indicating high temperature and low humidity. Site 3 showed a temperature of 34°C and humidity of 26%, representing moderate temperature and low humidity conditions.

The results demonstrate that the AGRISHELCRO-STRHASIS is capable of accurately monitoring temperature and humidity variations across different locations. This capability is essential for optimizing plant growth conditions, as both temperature and humidity significantly influence crop development. Moreover, the data can support decision-making processes, such as activating shading mechanisms or adjusting irrigation strategies to mitigate the effects of high temperature and low humidity.

Farmers' Evaluation of the AGRISHELCRO-STRHASIS

This section presents the evaluation of the AGRISHELCRO-STRHASIS based on the responses of the farmer-participants. The evaluation aimed to assess the system's performance, functionality, and usability based on environmental monitoring and response, resource management and efficiency, and system impact on plant growth and health.

Table 13. Farmers' Evaluation of the AGRISHEL CRO-STRH ASIS

Category	Statement	Weight Mean	Interpretation
Environmental Monitoring and Response	The system effectively assesses whether temperature poses a risk to plant health.	4.00	Strongly Agree
	The system automatically shades plants when high temperature is detected.	4.00	Strongly Agree
	The system responds appropriately to environmental changes affecting the plants.	4.00	Strongly Agree
	The system accurately detects rainfall occurrence.	4.00	Strongly Agree
	Mean	4.00	Strongly Agree
Resource Management and Efficiency	The system provides the proper amount of water needed for a healthy plant.	4.00	Strongly Agree
	The system effectively tracks sunlight to capture more solar energy.	4.00	Strongly Agree
	The system effectively saves electricity through the use of solar energy.	4.00	Strongly Agree
	The system automatically collects and utilizes rainwater when needed.	4.00	Strongly Agree
	Mean	4.00	Strongly Agree
Resource Management and Efficiency	The system effectively maintains plant growth rate and yield.	3.33	Strongly Agree
	The system positively impacts the overall health of the plants.	3.33	Strongly Agree
	Mean	3.33	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean		3.78	Strongly Agree

Note 3.25 – 4.00: Strongly Agree, 2.50 – 3.24: Agree, 1.75 – 2.49: Disagree, 1.00 – 1.74: Strongly Disagree

Table 13 presents the farmers' evaluation of the AGRISHEL CRO-STRH ASIS in terms of environmental monitoring and response, resource management and efficiency, and system impact on plant growth and health. The results indicate a consistently high level of agreement among the participants, with an overall mean of 3.78, interpreted as Strongly Agree. In terms of environmental monitoring and response, the system obtained a perfect category mean of 4.00, indicating that farmers strongly agreed that the system effectively detects temperature risks, responds to environmental changes, and accurately identifies rainfall conditions. This suggests that the system is reliable in monitoring environmental factors that directly affect crop health.

Similarly, resource management and efficiency also received a mean of 4.00, reflecting strong agreement on the system's ability to optimize water usage, utilize solar energy, and efficiently collect and store rainwater. These findings highlight the system's capability to promote sustainable agricultural practices by reducing resource wastage and improving energy efficiency. For system impact on plant growth and health, the category mean of 3.33, although slightly lower, still falls under Strongly Agree. This indicates that farmers perceived

the system as beneficial in maintaining plant growth and overall plant health. The slightly lower rating compared to other categories may suggest that observable effects on plant growth require a longer period of implementation.

Conclusions

This study was able to design and evaluate the effectiveness of the AGRISHEL-CRO-STRHASIS: A Solar-Powered IoT-Based Smart Irrigation and Shading System for Small-Scale Farming. The findings revealed that the system effectively monitors key environmental parameters, including temperature, soil moisture, and rainfall, enabling accurate and timely responses to changing conditions. The automated shading mechanism successfully protects plants from excessive heat, while the irrigation system delivers the appropriate amount of water based on soil moisture levels, preventing both overwatering and underwatering.

In addition, the integration of solar tracking enhances energy efficiency by maximizing solar energy capture, thereby reducing dependence on conventional electricity sources. The system also demonstrated effective rainwater harvesting and utilization, contributing to water conservation. Furthermore, the overall evaluation by farmer-participants indicated a high level of acceptance, particularly in terms of environmental monitoring, resource management, and system usability. Although the perceived impact on plant growth and health was slightly lower compared to other aspects, it still reflected a positive contribution to crop development. The AGRISHEL-CRO-STRHASIS proved to be a reliable, efficient, and sustainable agricultural system with strong potential for improving crop management and supporting small-scale farming operations.

Contributions of Authors

The authors indicate equal contributions to each section. The authors reviewed and approved the final work.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest regarding this paper.

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